

Ligand sensitized fluorescence of uranyl in its fluoride complex by picolinic acid : An application for trace fluoride ion determination

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Abstract : Picolinic acid has been used to form complex with uranyl fluoride to enhance the fluorescence intensity by about two times. Linearity in fluorescence intensity of uranyl-fluoride-picolinate complex was obtained in the range of fluoride concentration of 40–400 ppb. The quenching effect of ions like Cl^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , CO_3^{2-} and Fe^{2+} on the fluorescence intensity of uranyl-fluoride and uranyl-fluoride-picolinate complexes have been studied. Stern-Volmer quenching constants for these quenchers were found to be about five times less in uranyl-fluoride-picolinate complex as compared to uranyl-fluoride complex. Fe^{2+} ion is found to have severe quenching effects on the fluorescence intensity of both the complexes of uranyl. This method can be used for determination of trace amount of fluoride in water samples with the tolerance limits of NO_3^- (20 ppm), SO_4^{2-} (60 ppm), CO_3^{2-} (100 ppm) and Cl^- (2 ppm).

Keywords : Fluorescence, uranyl, fluoride, picolinic acid.

Introduction

Determination of fluoride ion (F^-) concentration is very important in various fields such as environmental, health sciences etc.¹. Fluoride has some beneficial effects to human body such as dental caries, if it is present within some specific limit, but it shows toxic effects if it is present in large concentration². It has been known that fluorosis is caused by elevated intake of fluoride over prolonged period of time and mostly drinking water is the major contributor for fluoride intake. Ion selective electrode based methods of fluoride ion determination in materials like drinking water, fruit juice, tooth paste etc. are often found in literature^{3,4}.

Uranyl ion (UO_2^{2+} ; in the text it will be presented as U) is known to make strong complexes with fluoride ion and these uranyl fluoride (U-F) complexes can be characterized by fluorescence spectroscopy as they show fluorescence in aqueous medium⁵⁻⁷. Uranyl ion is often found to exhibit fluorescence enhancement when complexed with suitable organic ligands^{8,9}. The fluorescence enhancement is due to efficient energy transfer from the triplet level of ligand to the lowest lying emitting level of metal ion, a phenomenon known as ligand sensitized fluorescence⁸⁻¹¹. In this study, picolinic acid (PA) has been used as ligand for enhancing the fluorescence of U-F complex. In this paper, we made use of the enhanced fluorescence of

uranyl fluoride picolinate (U-F-PA) complex for the estimation of F^- concentration in water. Quenching effects due to the presence of different ions on the fluorescence have also been studied.

Results and discussion

Fluorescence of U-F complex :

Fig. 1a and 1b shows the excitation spectra of uncomplexed uranium (without F^-) and U-F complex in water respectively. These spectra were recorded by fixing the emission wavelength at 515 nm. The concentration of F^- in U-F complex was 1 ppm. The excitation spectra (Fig. 1a and 1b) are similar indicating that the absorbing specie is uranyl in both the cases. Fluorescence emission spectra for U and U-F are recorded with excitation at 255 nm and are shown in Fig. 2a and 2b, respectively. In the presence of F^- , emission from U displays well resolved spectral lines (Fig. 2b) with peak positions at 495, 515, 542 and 568 nm and the fluorescence intensity is enhanced. Similar observations of fluorescence enhancement has been reported in the literature⁶. The fluoride ions prevent the water molecules nearing the U ion there by reducing the quenching effects and resulting in an enhancement in fluorescence intensity.

Fig. 1. Excitation spectra of (a) U; (b) U-F; (c) U-F-PA, U - 5 ppm; F - 1 ppm; PA - 3×10^{-4} M.

Fig. 2. Emission spectra of (a) U; (b) U-F; (c) U-F-PA, U - 5 ppm; F - 1 ppm; PA - 3×10^{-4} M.

Fluorescence of U-F-PA complex :

At the outset, the fluorescence of U was recorded as a function of PA concentration and pH of the solution. Maximum fluorescence intensity was obtained for pH 4.5 (Fig. 3) and acid concentration of 3×10^{-4} M of PA. This acid concentration and pH was used throughout this study. The excitation and emission spectrum of U-F in the presence of PA, at pH 4.5, is shown in Fig. 1c and 2c, respectively. The excitation maximum for U-F-PA (Fig. 1c) occurs at 272 nm, which is different from excitation maximum for U and U-F of 255 nm (Fig. 1a and 1b). This indicates that the absorber in the U-F-PA com-

Fig. 3. The variation of fluorescence intensity of U-F-PA with pH of the solution; U - 5 ppm, F - 1 ppm, PA - 3×10^{-4} M.

plex is different from that of U-F case and it is likely that PA which is absorbing light. The emission spectrum shown in Fig. 2c, over the range 460–580 nm, recorded using excitation at 272 nm, displays well resolved features as displayed by U-F complex. We have also carried out experiments in which only U and PA solutions are mixed (without the fluoride). We have not observed any enhancement in the uranium fluorescence. It is clear from the emission spectra (Fig. 2b and 2c) that PA enhances the fluorescence of U-F by about two times. These observations strongly indicate a complex formation between U-F and PA.

Linear range and detection limit :

The fluorescence intensity of U-F-PA complex was

Fig. 4. Calibration curve for fluorescence intensity of U-F-PA complex in water; U - 5 ppm, PA - 3×10^{-4} M, pH 4.5.

found to increase linearly with F^- concentration which makes it useful for the trace determination of fluoride ion. Linearity in fluorescence intensity of this U-F-PA complex was obtained in the range of fluoride ion concentration of 40–400 ppb which is shown in Fig. 4. The detection limit calculated using the criterion of 3σ of the

blank is 12 ppb. The relative standard deviation for 5 replicate analysis of the sample containing 40 ppb of fluoride ion is $\sim 8\%$.

Effect of ions :

In order to apply this method for F^- determination in water samples, it is necessary to see the effects of pres-

Fig. 5. Stern-Volmer plots for U-F and U-F-PA complexes with different ions : (a) SO_4^{2-} ; (b) CO_3^{2-} ; (c) NO_3^- ; (d) Cl^- ; (e) Fe^{2+} ; U - 5 ppm; F - 1 ppm; PA - 3×10^{-4} M for all cases.

ence of other ions which are commonly found in water, on the fluorescence intensity of U-F-PA complex. Different ions such as Cl^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , CO_3^{2-} and Fe^{2+} were used for this study and found to quench the fluorescence intensity. Quenching behaviour of different ions can be obtained from Stern-Volmer equation¹²:

$$I_0 / I = 1 + k_D [Q]$$

where I_0 and I are the fluorescence intensity of the complex without quencher and with quencher respectively, k_D represents the Stern-Volmer constant for a particular ion, and $[Q]$ is the concentration of quencher. In Fig. 5, $[(I_0/I) - 1]$ is plotted against the quencher concentration. Stern-Volmer plots for these ions are not linear which indicates the presence of both static and collision type of quenching operating in this system¹². SO_4^{2-} and CO_3^{2-} ions (Fig. 5a and 5b) have less quenching effect as compared to NO_3^- and Cl^- which are found to have drastic quenching effect even at low concentrations as shown in Fig. 5d and 5e respectively. The fluorescence intensity is decreased by about 25% at 500 ppm of SO_4^{2-} . The same effect is seen for CO_3^{2-} when the concentration is 250 ppm. The quenching effect of ions on the fluorescence of U-F in absence of PA is also studied and plotted in the same Fig. 5. It is clear from these plots that the quenching effects of these ions, except Fe^{2+} , are more severe in case of U-F than the case of U-F-PA. Fe^{2+} was found to have severe quenching effect in both the complexes as can be seen from Fig. 5e. Tolerance limits of different ions, which caused the maximum reduction in fluorescence intensity of U-F-PA by 10% were calculated and found to be NO_3^- (20 ppm), SO_4^{2-} (60 ppm), CO_3^{2-} (100 ppm) and Cl^- (2 ppm) for the determination of 200 ppb of F^- .

In summary picolinic acid was found to enhance the fluorescence of uranyl fluoride complex. Also fluorescence quenching by other ions was observed to be less in case of U-F-PA as compared to U-F complex, which could lead the fluoride ion determination in trace levels.

Experimental

All fluorescence spectra were recorded using an Edinburgh FLS920 spectrofluorimeter, with a 450 W xenon lamp source. Solutions were taken in a 10 mm path length fused silica cell. The band-pass for the excitation and emission monochromators was set at 2 nm each. A long-wavelength pass filter (UV-39, Shimadzu), with a

maximum and uniform transmittance (> 85%) above 400 nm, was placed in front of the emission monochromator to reduce the scatter of the incident beam entering the emission monochromator. Spectra were recorded at room temperature with a 90° collection geometry. All spectra had been corrected for instrument response.

Standard solutions of uranium was prepared by dissolving the required amount of uranium oxide in distilled HClO_4 . Stock solution of fluoride ion was prepared by dissolving the required amount of sodium fluoride in water. All the ions like Cl^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , CO_3^{2-} were prepared from their highly pure sodium salt by dissolving in distilled water. Stock solution of picolinic acid (Sigma Aldrich) was prepared by dissolving the required amount of the reagent in water. All chemicals were used as purchased from the supplier without any further purification. De-ionized water (18 M Ω) obtained with a Milli-Q (Millipore) system was used in preparing all solutions.

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